

MANAGEMENT IN JOURNALISM

Dadakhan Raimbayev

Karakalpak State University

Karakalpak philology and journalism

student of the 4th stage of the faculty

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7030946>

Annotation: this article is written about the management management and economics of the editorial office on internet sites.

Keywords: online, management, newspaper, internet, media:

The development of the internet today led to the development of the media in the internet system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the aspirations of the organization in the information society. Their difference from ordinary media is that the first is the fact that it is included in the mass audience has a wide coverage, corporate character. Traditionally, the media include the following. Press, TV, advertising, banners and panels today, Western countries have fully included the internet in the type of media. But if we look at national journalism, we cannot include the internet as a 100% media type. Only part of it today performs the function of the media source information of standard material working according to the user or consumer scheme. In this regard, the result communication occurs in different manifestations. From a 3-period page to an email, the source here is only one person or a group of journalists if the information can be journalistic material or a small informational text on the site. The user or consumer can also have an audience. In order to independently conduct commercial and business activities, the editorial office must be in the status of a legal entity. To do this, the editorial board must be registered by the founder as an economic entity in local government bodies, choosing one of the forms provided for by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This is what determines the development of economic relations between the founder and the editorial board. In particular, the owner of the editorial property is answered such questions as how financial funds are used and how the profit is distributed between whom. These organizational and legal forms are divided into two parts. Forms relating to the first part are selected by the founder one condition the main purpose of which should not be solely profit-making in this case, the editorial state institution is registered in a non-profit organization or other form. While Mobodo's goal of making financial profit comes first, the editorial limited liability company is registered in the form of a private enterprise or Joint-Stock Company. The specifics of each of its forms are manifested in the work of

publishing and brand ownership and ownership of the name of the newspaper, as well as the fact that the editorial office has its own stamp on the account in banking institutions on an independent balance of ownership of editorial property and profit from entrepreneurial business activities. Also, the organizational and legal form of the internet editorial office as a legal entity is also visible in the specific aspects of the team management of the relations of the Founder Editor-in-chief, established by its charter. Media editorial management goal form and organizational aspects does not take into account the requirements of mass media management. It is impossible to engage in Media business in this place, management is understood as two things. Firstly the management of the editorial team is the process of the method of forms secondly the managers who make up the belt of leaders who manage the team of people of a particular profession the economic factor has a strong influence on the entire process of editorial management. Determines the direction and character of the goal of management since the relatively free functioning of the image in its existence will depend on its economic independence. The main goal of most of its leaders is to see financial profit remains to strengthen the economic base of the publication. For this reason, editorial management and editorial management are of an economic nature. It takes the form of economic management of all its employees of the team, and for the second purpose it consists in the formation in all employees of the editorial board of economic thinking of the feeling that their activities affect the editorial economic base. Now the editorial leadership acts in its management based on several economic principles. The first of them ensures that the internet media can survive only if the benefits of the internet publication bring financial benefits. Therefore, the activities of all its employees will be directed to this goal. The second principle is that ensuring its competitiveness is also in fact inextricably linked with the desire to make a profit since it is possible to make a profit only by enduring strong competition with publications from other internet systems. The third principle is to provide economic savings that is, less effort on the activities of editorial management is aimed at achieving its goals by using energy tools and funds. Austerity in all areas of activity ensures the achievement of the desired results in a short way at the time.

References:

- 1.Modern internet journalism” Turayev Nurbek
- 2.Social Institute of journalism “ Fayzulla Muminov
- 3.Online Journalism and media” Nargiz Kasimova
- 4.Audiojournalism” Amirullo Karimov